

The Influence of Emotional Intelligence, Professionalism, and Individual Characteristics on the Performance of Employees of the Investment Agency, Integrated One-Stop Service, Trans-Migration, and Labor in the Balangan Regency, South Kalimantan Province

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ABSTRACT: This study aims to examine the influence of Emotional Intelligence, Professionalism, and Individual Characteristics on the Performance of Employees of the Investment Agency, Integrated One-Stop Service, Trans-Migration, and Labor in the Balangan Regency, South Kalimantan Province. The population in this study consists of employees of the Investment and Integrated One-Stop Service Agency, Transmigration, and Labor Office in Balangan Regency, totaling 109 individuals. The sampling method used in this research is the census method. The selection of the census method in this study is based on the consideration that all employees of the Investment and Integrated One-Stop Service Agency, Transmigration, and Labor Office in Balangan Regency amount to 109 individuals. Therefore, the entire population is used as the sample. The data analysis used in this research is multiple linear regression with statistical tools facilitated by the IBM SPSS v.21 program. The results of this study indicate that Emotional Intelligence, Professionalism, and Individual Characteristics have an influence on Performance of Employees of the Investment Agency, Integrated One-Stop Service, Trans-Migration, and Labor in the Balangan Regency, South Kalimantan Province. The Individual Characteristics variable has a dominant influence on the on Performance of Employees of the Investment Agency, Integrated One-Stop Service, Trans-Migration, and Labor in the Balangan Regency, South Kalimantan Province.

KEYWORDS: Emotional Intelligence, Individual Characteristics, Professionalism, Performance of Employees.

INTRODUCTION

emotional intelligence and professionalism as influential factors in the performance of employees in the Investment and Integrated One-Stop Service Agency, Transmigration, and Labor in Balangan Regency, South Kalimantan. Emotional intelligence, encompassing self-awareness, self-regulation, motivation, empathy, and social skills, is considered crucial in executing tasks, especially in public services. Employees need to manage their emotions effectively, particularly when interacting with the public and new colleagues. Furthermore, good emotional intelligence is linked to the ability to make firm decisions, think clearly under pressure, and understand others' perspectives. Professionalism is also deemed crucial in the context of public services, where employees are expected to have the conviction that their actions are based on knowledge and professional values that prioritize the public interest. Professionalism includes adherence to the law, neutrality, rationality, innovation, integrity, and the application of public administration ethics. Each bureaucrat is perceived to need high competence, encompassing knowledge and skills to perform tasks effectively and efficiently. Additionally, adaptation to contemporary challenges and continuous development in professionalism, commitment, and high integrity are considered essential to ensure quality public services.

The importance of professional attitude, emotional intelligence, and individual characteristics in improving employee performance, particularly in the Investment and Integrated One-Stop Service Agency, Transmigration, and Labor Office in Balangan Regency, South Kalimantan, is emphasized. Professionalism is considered a mandatory requirement for employees, emphasizing understanding relationships, responsibilities, and consistency in their work. The presence of a professional attitude is expected to have a positive impact, both for the office and the community in need of services. In addition, emotional intelligence is considered a crucial aspect, including self-awareness, self-regulation, motivation, empathy, and social skills. Good emotional intelligence is seen to support making decisive decisions, resilience under pressure, and understanding others' perspectives, especially in the context of public services in the Investment and Integrated One-Stop Service Agency and related sectors. Individual characteristics,

such as interests, attitudes, values, and abilities, are also highlighted as factors influencing employee performance. Differences in individual characteristics among employees require understanding and cooperation in the workplace to achieve organizational goals. Leaders are expected to understand these differences and create an environment that supports employee motivation.

The importance of meeting individual needs and stimulating other aspects not solely dependent on salary or bonuses is emphasized as an effort to improve job performance. Individual job performance is considered the basis for organizational job performance, and stimuli need to consider individual characteristics and the work environment that create supportive conditions. Overall, job performance is defined as the result of work that aligns with authority and responsibilities, achieves organizational goals legally, and does not violate ethics. All these factors are explained in the context of the Investment and Integrated One-Stop Service Agency, Transmigration, and Labor Office in Balangan Regency, with an emphasis on the importance of developing employee self-quality through increased skills and knowledge.

The organizational target achievements outlined in the Goals and Indicators of the Investment and Integrated One-Stop Service Agency, Transmigration, and Labor Office in Balangan Regency have not reached 100%. In the investment realization indicator, the achievement is only 50.65%, totaling IDR 115.122 million, while the Open Unemployment Rate indicator has not yet reached the target, standing at 2.44 or 99.19%. The above indicators are targets that must be collectively implemented by all employees to ensure a high organizational assessment. This involves realizing the predetermined work targets set by the Balangan Regency Government. The low achievement in investment improvement is attributed to the low investment figures in Balangan Regency, but the unemployment rate has been reduced.

Moreover, each year, Civil Servant employees receive a direct assessment from superiors in the form of Work Target Evaluation, Behavior Value, and Job Achievement Value for the last 3 years. The average SKP assessment of the Investment and Integrated One-Stop Service Agency, Transmigration, and Labor Office in Balangan Regency, South Kalimantan, has increased annually. This increase is due to career development requirements, such as promotions, which necessitate continuous improvement in assessments.

Based on the background described above, the problem formulations that can be derived are:

1. Does Emotional Intelligence, Professionalism, and Individual Characteristics significantly influence the Employee Performance of the Investment and Integrated One-Stop Service Agency, Transmigration, and Labor Office in Balangan Regency, South Kalimantan Province, simultaneously?
2. Do Emotional Intelligence, Professionalism, and Individual Characteristics significantly influence the Employee Performance of the Investment and Integrated One-Stop Service Agency, Transmigration, and Labor Office in Balangan Regency, South Kalimantan Province, partially?
3. Which variable has a dominant influence on the Employee Performance of the Investment and Integrated One-Stop Service Agency, Transmigration, and Labor Office in Balangan Regency, South Kalimantan Province?

LITERATURE REVIEW

a. *Human Resources Management*

Human Resources (HR) is one of the assets owned by a company and is a key element in the operational activities of the company. HR becomes something of high value when managed well by the company's management. This aligns with Sedarmayanti's opinion (2017:3), stating that Human Resource Management (HRM) is the process of harnessing human beings as human resources in a humane manner so that all physical and psychological potentials function maximally to achieve goals. Meanwhile, according to Handoko (2001:88) as cited in Purnaya (2016:2), Human Resource Management (HRM) is a process of planning, organizing, directing, and controlling activities related to the acquisition, development, compensation, integration, maintenance, and release of human resources to achieve various individual, organizational, and societal goals. Another perspective is offered by Hasibuan (2017:10), stating that Human Resource Management (HRM) is the science and art of organizing the relationships and roles of the workforce effectively and efficiently to help achieve the goals of the company, employees, and society.

According to Malayu S.P. Hasibuan (2016:21-23), the functions of human resource management are Planning, Organizing, Directing, Controlling, Acquisition, Development, Compensation, Integration, Maintenance, Discipline, and Termination.

According to Hasibuan (2016:9-10), the similarity between Human Resource Management and personnel management is that both are sciences that regulate human elements within an organization to support the achievement of goals. However, the differences between Human Resource Management and personnel management are as follows:

1. Human Resource Management is studied on a macro level, while personnel management is studied on a micro level.
2. Human Resource Management considers employees as the main asset of the organization, so they must be well maintained. Personnel management sees employees as a factor of production, so they must be utilized productively.
3. Human Resource Management follows a modern approach, while personnel management follows a classical approach.

b. Emotional Intelligence

According to Bar-On (2007:82) et al., emotional intelligence is defined as a set of personal, emotional, and social abilities that influence an individual's capability to succeed in coping with environmental demands and pressures (Sumiyarsih et al., 2012:22). According to Salovey & Mayer (1999:31) in the journal by Martha Bethania Prajna P. Habel Prihastuti (2019:41), emotional intelligence is defined as the ability to regulate one's own feelings and emotions, distinguish and use this information to guide an individual's thoughts and actions (Martha Bethania, 2013:3).

1. Attitude towards their profession
2. Adaptation to colleagues and work environment
3. Reactive behavior towards leadership policies

According to Goleman (2009) as cited in Nurita (2012:16), factors influencing emotional intelligence include:

1. Genetic Factors: Inherent genetic factors, such as temperament. There are four temperaments, namely fearful, brave, cheerful, and contemplative.
2. Environmental Factors: Family life serves as our first school to learn about emotions. In this familiar environment, we learn how to sense our own feelings, how others respond to our feelings, how to think about these emotions, the choices we have to react, and how to read and express expectations and fears.

Daniel Goleman (2015:72) outlines indicators of emotional intelligence as follows:

1. Recognizing one's own emotions
2. Managing emotions
3. Self-motivation
4. Recognizing the emotions of others
5. Building relationships

c. Work Professionalism

Work professionalism is the reliability and expertise in performing tasks with high quality, timely execution, accuracy, and with easily understandable procedures (Siagian, 2012:21). The ability and expertise in carrying out tasks to achieve high quality, timely execution, accuracy, and in accordance with the procedures set by the company (Fajar et al., 2015:12).

According to Budi Rajab (1990:82) (as cited in Fitri Wirjayanti, 2014:21), professionalism is highly needed in an organization. A professional human resource is required to create good capabilities and commitment from the individuals working in the organization, while also fostering the organization's image. Law Number 43 of 1999 concerning amendments to Law Number 8 of 1974 concerning the principles of civil servants, in Article 17 paragraph 2, regulates the appointment of civil servants to a position based on the principles of professionalism according to competence, work performance, and the rank structure determined for that position, as well as other objective requirements without distinguishing gender, ethnicity, religion, and group. A civil servant must have professionalism because of several demands, including:

1. The tasks, duties, functions, authorities, and responsibilities that must be carried out, such as providing public services.
2. Implementation of good governance.
3. In an effort to balance rapidly changing strategic environments, both internal and external to the organization.
4. The ongoing developments in science, technology, and the era of globalization cannot be prevented and rejected.

d. Individual Characteristics

According to James (2004:21), individual characteristics are the interests, attitudes, and needs that an individual brings into a

work situation. Ivancevich (2008:65) defines individual characteristics as those who perceive various things differently will behave differently, individuals with different attitudes will respond differently to orders, and interact differently with superiors, colleagues, and subordinates. Every person has individual characteristics that differ from one another. Individual characteristics can describe the distinctive features inherent in a person's actions and behaviors, especially in their conduct. Ardana (2008:12) states that individual characteristics are behaviors or traits that exist in an individual employee, whether positive or negative. Hasibuan (2005:24) describes individual characteristics as inherent traits that can be changed by the environment or education.

Individual characteristics are the most identified traits of an employee. Factors within individual characteristics, according to Robbins (1990:92) in Setiawan (2013:57), consist of age, gender, marital status, education level, and length of employment in the company. According to Robbins (2001:72), the factors mentioned above will be explained as follows: an employee who is older will have a high commitment to the company because advancing age makes it difficult for the employee to find another job (Robbins, 2008:63).

Humans are divided into two genders, women and men, which can determine the progress of a company. According to Robbins (1997:21) in Setiawan (2013:58), men and women do not have differences in solving a problem, analytical skills, motivation, competitive drive, sociability, or learning ability. Robbins (2001:21) in Setiono (2017:58) states that an increase in job responsibility becomes essential and valuable due to marital status. Meanwhile, length of employment is a significant variable in explaining the turnover of employees; according to Robbins (2008:30), a person who has worked in a place for a long time is unlikely to resign. Human resource development can be seen from the aspect of the level of education of the workforce because the level of education is closely related to the improvement of employee performance (Setiono, 2016:148). This is considering that a more educated workforce will have broader insights, encouraging individuals to take more profound actions in their work. As stated by Idris (2015:414), negative assumptions about the age of an employee, the older they are, the greater the absenteeism value of their employees, especially if the older employee has an ailment that requires a longer healing time compared to younger employees.

e. Performance of Employee

According to Mubarak (2017:77), performance is the result or level of success of an individual or group of people in carrying out tasks over a specific period compared to various possibilities, work standards, target objectives, or predetermined and agreed-upon criteria. Thus, performance is the readiness of an individual or group of people to perform an activity and perfect it according to responsibilities and expected outcomes. Employees are a crucial part of a company because they are directly involved in making the company successful. Basically, every employee must have the skills that align with their performance within the company. According to Mangkunegara (2017:67) as cited in Juniarti and Indahingwati (2020:12), performance is the qualitative and quantitative work results achieved by an employee in carrying out their duties in accordance with the responsibilities assigned to them. Every company wants employees who produce good performance, so various efforts will be made by the company to improve the performance of its employees.

According to Sedarmayanti (2011:262), performance appraisal is a formal system for periodically examining and evaluating an individual's performance. The objectives of conducting performance appraisals are as follows:

1. Improve employee performance by helping them become aware of and use their full potential in achieving organizational goals.
2. Provide information to employees and leaders as a basis for making work-related decisions. According to Law No. 5 of 2014 concerning State Civil Apparatus, the performance appraisal of civil servants aims to ensure the objectivity of civil service development based on performance and career systems, considering targets, achievements, results, and benefits achieved, as well as the behavior of civil servants. Performance appraisal of civil servants is one crucial step in the cycle of resource development conducted objectively, measurably, accountably, participatively, and transparently.

f. *Conceptual Framework*

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

g. *Hypothesis*

The hypothesis proposed in this research is:

- H1: Emotional Intelligence, Work Professionalism, and Individual Characteristics have a significant simultaneous effect on the Performance of employees of the Investment and Integrated One-Stop Service Agency, Transmigration, and Labor Office in Balangan Regency, South Kalimantan Province.
- H2: Emotional Intelligence, Work Professionalism, and Individual Characteristics have a significant partial effect on the Performance of employees of the Investment and Integrated One-Stop Service Agency, Transmigration, and Labor Office in Balangan Regency, South Kalimantan Province.
- H3: Individual Characteristics (X3) is the dominant influential variable on the Performance of employees of the Investment and Integrated One-Stop Service Agency, Transmigration, and Labor Office in Balangan Regency, South Kalimantan Province.

RESEARCH METHOD

This research is a quantitative correlational study, which examines the relationship between independent and dependent variables. The population in this study consists of employees of the Investment and Integrated One-Stop Service Agency, Transmigration, and Labor Office in Balangan Regency, totaling 109 individuals. The sampling method used in this research is the census method. The selection of the census method in this study is based on the consideration that all employees of the Investment and Integrated One-Stop Service Agency, Transmigration, and Labor Office in Balangan Regency amount to 109 individuals. Therefore, the entire population is used as the sample. The data analysis used in this research is multiple linear regression with statistical tools facilitated by the IBM SPSS v.21 program.

RESULT

Validity Test

Table 1. The Result of Validity Test

Variabel	Item	R	Keterangan
Emotional Intelligence (X1)	X1.1	0,895	Valid
	X1.2	0,895	Valid
	X1.3	0,839	Valid
	X1.4	0,804	Valid
	X1.5	0,586	Valid

Variabel	Item	R	Keterangan
Work Professionalism (X2)	X1.1	0,910	Valid
	X1.2	0,922	Valid
	X1.3	0,891	Valid
Individual Characteristics (X3)	X3.1	0,819	Valid
	X3.2	0,940	Valid
	X3.3	0,908	Valid
	X3.4	0,912	Valid
Performance of employees (Y)	Y.1	0,738	Valid
	Y.2	0,895	Valid
	Y.3	0,960	Valid
	Y.4	0,960	Valid
	Y.5	0,895	Valid
	Y.6	0,960	
	Y.7	0,960	
	Y.8	0,756	

Source: Primary data processed

Based on the validity test in Table 1 above, in the validity test, all questionnaire items are declared valid because all questionnaire items have correlation values greater than the required r value of 0.3.

Reliability Test

Table 2. The Result of Reliability Test

No	Variable	Cronbach's alpha	Description
1	Emotional Intelligence (X1)	0,868	Reliable
2	Work Professionalism (X2)	0,893	Reliable
3	Individual Characteristics (X3)	0,916	Reliable
4	Performance of employees (Y)	0,963	Reliable

Source: Primary data processed.

Based on the results of the reliability test in this study, the reliability value of all instruments is accepted or reliable because it has a minimum Cronbach's Alpha and Cronbach's Alpha If Item Deleted values greater than the reliability standard, which is 0.6.

Multiple Linear Regression

The testing was conducted with a confidence level of 95% or a significance level of 0.05 ($\alpha = 0.05$). To examine the validity of these hypotheses, multiple linear regression analysis was employed. In this regression analysis, both simultaneous or F-test and partial or t-test will be conducted.

Table 3. Multiple Linear Regression Test

Variable	Regression Coefficient (bi)	t count	t table	Beta	sig
Constant	4,650				
Emotional Intelligence (X1)	0,474	2,920	1,660	0,265	0,004
Work Professionalism (X2)	0,966	3,681	1,660	0,319	0,000
Individual Characteristics (X3)	0,456	3,221	1,660	0,301	0,002

Constant = 4,650	F count = 12,594
Multiple R = 0,514	F table = 2,46
R square (R ²) = 0,265	Sig = 0,000

Source: Primary data processed.

The interpretation of the constant (4.650) in this study, where variables are measured using a Likert scale ranging from 1 to 5, should not be interpreted that if the variables Emotional Intelligence (X1), Work Professionalism (X2), and Individual Characteristics (X3) have a value of zero. This is because these three variables cannot have a value of zero since the lowest Likert scale used is 1. Based on the SPSS calculation in this study, the constant value is 4.650, which falls into the good category.

In Table 4, the R Square is 0.265, indicating that the variation contributed by all independent variables to the dependent variable is 26.5%, while the remaining 73.5% is explained by other factors outside of this study. The R Square value of 0.265 or 26.5% indicates a moderately strong correlation between the independent variables Emotional Intelligence (X1), Work Professionalism (X2), and Individual Characteristics (X3) with the Performance (Y) of employees of the Department of Investment and Integrated One-Door Services, Transmigration, and Manpower of Balangan Regency, South Kalimantan Province.

Based on Table 4, the regression equation obtained is as follows:

$$Y = 4,650 + 0,474 X1 + 0,966 X2 + 0,456 X3 + e$$

Based on the results of the equation above, it can be interpreted as follows:

1. If the coefficient of 0.474 for the variable Emotional Intelligence (X1) increases, assuming the coefficients of 0.966 for Work Professionalism (X2) and 0.456 for Individual Characteristics (X3) remain constant, then Performance (Y) will also increase.
2. If the coefficient of 0.966 for the variable Work Professionalism (X2) increases, assuming the coefficients of 0.474 for Emotional Intelligence (X1) and 0.456 for Individual Characteristics (X3) remain constant, then Performance (Y) will also increase.
3. If the coefficient of 0.456 for the variable Individual Characteristics (X3) increases, assuming the coefficients of 0.474 for Emotional Intelligence (X1) and 0.966 for Work Professionalism (X2) remain constant, then Performance (Y) will also increase.

Based on this equation, it is evident that all independent variables have positive regression coefficients. This implies that the variables Emotional Intelligence (X1), Work Professionalism (X2), and Individual Characteristics (X3) have a direct or proportional relationship with the dependent variable, Performance (Y). In other words, if variables X1, X2, and X3 increase, the dependent variable Y will also increase, and if variables X1, X2, and X3 decrease, the dependent variable Y will decrease.

Hypothesis Testing

Decision-making or hypothesis testing in this research involves using the t-test (partial) and the F-test (simultaneous). The results of the partial t-test and the simultaneous F-test in this study can be seen as follows:

1. t-Test

Through this test, it will be determined whether the variables consisting of Emotional Intelligence (X1) affect the Performance (Y) at the Department of Investment and Integrated One-Door Services, Transmigration, and Manpower of Balangan Regency, South Kalimantan Province. This is done by comparing the calculated t-value with the t-table, at a significance level (confidence level) of 5% and the degrees of freedom formula, $df = n - K - 1 = 109 - 4 - 1 = 104$, then the t-table value is found to be 1.660. If the calculated t-value is greater than the t-table value, then its influence is significant. Additionally, it can also be observed how much each independent variable influences its dependent variable.

The influence of the Emotional Intelligence variable (X1) on Performance (Y): Emotional Intelligence (X1) significantly influences Performance (Y) because the calculated t-value (2.920) > t-table (1.660). Therefore, it can be concluded that Emotional Intelligence (X1) has a significant influence individually or partially on Performance (Y) at the Department of Investment and Integrated One-Door Services, Transmigration, and Manpower of Balangan Regency, South Kalimantan Province.

The influence of the Work Professionalism variable (X2) on Performance (Y): Work Professionalism (X2) significantly influences

Performance (Y) as evidenced by the table (3.681) > t-table (1.660). Consequently, it can be inferred that Work Professionalism (X2) has a significant individual or partial influence on Performance (Y) at the Department of Investment and Integrated One-Door Services, Transmigration, and Manpower of Balangan Regency, South Kalimantan Province.

The influence of the Individual Characteristics variable (X3) on Performance (Y): Individual Characteristics (X3) significantly influence Performance (Y) as shown by the table (3.221) > t-table (1.660). Hence, it can be concluded that Individual Characteristics (X3) have a significant individual or partial influence on Performance (Y) at the Department of Investment and Integrated One-Door Services, Transmigration, and Manpower of Balangan Regency, South Kalimantan Province.

Thus, the second hypothesis stating that Emotional Intelligence, Work Professionalism, and Individual Characteristics have a significant partial influence on the Performance of employees at the Department of Investment and Integrated One-Door Services, Transmigration, and Manpower of Balangan Regency, South Kalimantan Province, is correct or verified.

2. F-Test

This test is used with the aim of proving whether the independent variables collectively influence the dependent variable. In addressing the hypotheses proposed at the beginning of the study, the analysis tool utilized is the SPSS software version 21.00. The results of the calculations through SPSS show an F-value of 12.594, and the F-table, using a significance level (confidence level) of 5% and the degrees of freedom formula, $df_1 = K - 1 = 4 - 1 = 3$, and $df_2 = n - K = 109 - 4 = 105$. The obtained F-table value is 2.46.

This indicates that the F-value (12.594) > F-table (2.46), thus accepting or confirming the first hypothesis stating that Emotional Intelligence, Work Professionalism, and Individual Characteristics collectively and significantly influence the Performance of employees at the Department of Investment and Integrated One-Door Services, Transmigration, and Manpower of Balangan Regency, South Kalimantan Province.

3. Dominant Variabel

In the third hypothesis, which states that Individual Characteristics (X3) are the most influential factor on Performance (Y), the results of the study indicate that the variable Work Professionalism (X2) with a Beta Coefficient value of 0.319 is greater than the Beta Coefficient value of Individual Characteristics (X3) which is 0.301, and also greater than the Beta Coefficient value of Emotional Intelligence (X1), which is only 0.265.

This suggests that the third hypothesis, claiming that Individual Characteristics (X3) are the most influential factor on Performance (Y), is incorrect or not supported by the research findings. The study indicates that Work Professionalism (X2) has a higher Beta Coefficient, implying a relatively stronger influence on Performance (Y) compared to Emotional Intelligence (X1) and Individual Characteristics (X3).

DISCUSSION

Emotional Intelligence, Work Professionalism, and Individual Characteristics significantly influence the Employees' Performance simultaneously.

Based on the research findings in proving the first hypothesis, there is a significant influence of Emotional Intelligence, Work Professionalism, and Individual Characteristics simultaneously on the Employees' Performance in the Office of Investment and Integrated One-Stop Service, Transmigration, and Manpower of Balangan Regency, South Kalimantan Province. This research finding is a new discovery in this study, as there is no similar study with the same variables in previous research recommended in this study.

The performance of employees in the Office of Investment and Integrated One-Stop Service, Transmigration, and Manpower of Balangan Regency, South Kalimantan Province, will be good if the Emotional Intelligence of all employees is improved. Since employees often work directly with the public and other companies, performing tasks calmly without emotions will result in good and quality work. Additionally, employee professionalism must be upheld in all areas, including Service, Investment, Manpower, and Transmigration. All employees must work professionally, adhering to their promises and oaths when becoming civil servants (PNS) or in employment agreements for non-PNS employees. They should avoid violating work regulations, such as accepting gifts

or engaging in corrupt practices. Furthermore, Individual Characteristics play a crucial role. As each employee possesses unique characteristics, mutual understanding and acceptance are necessary. Acknowledging and understanding each other's strengths and weaknesses, working cooperatively, and avoiding favoritism contribute to a harmonious work environment.

Emotional Intelligence, Work Professionalism, and Individual Characteristics each have a significant partial effect on Employee Performance

Based on the research results as evidence of hypothesis II above, that Emotional Intelligence has a significant effect on the Performance of Employees of the Investment and Integrated One-Stop Services Office, Transmigration, and Labor of Balangan Regency, South Kalimantan Province. This research finding is in line with research conducted by Hetti Mariati Simangunsong (2021) on the Effect of Emotional Intelligence, Competence, Work Culture, and Job Satisfaction on Employee Performance at the Main Port Authority Office of Belawan. The data analysis technique used in this study is descriptive analysis and multiple linear regression analysis. The results of this study explain that emotional intelligence has a positive and significant effect on performance.

Competence has a positive and significant effect on performance. Work culture has a positive and significant effect on performance. Emotional intelligence, competence, work culture, and job satisfaction have a positive and significant effect on performance. Based on the frequency of responses from research respondents, the dominant answer to the Emotional Intelligence variable is that respondents agree if employees are self-aware in carrying out their work. Employees can self-regulate when working. Employees have motivation in working. Employees can recognize the emotions of others (empathy) at work, and employees have social skills at work. In the future, the emotional intelligence of employees must be good at work because every job must be done calmly and calmly to produce good and quality work. Additionally, employees in serving permits must not be emotional; they must remain calm even if the permit applicant is emotional. Employees must not be provoked; they must quickly calm down and provide empathetic understanding.

Work Professionalism has a significant effect on the Performance of Employees of the Investment and Integrated One-Stop Services Office, Transmigration, and Labor of Balangan Regency, South Kalimantan Province. The findings of this study are in line with research conducted by Nur Afrita (2018) on the Influence of Leadership Style, Professionalism, Work Environment, Emotional Intelligence, and Spiritual Intelligence on the Performance of Financial Managers at the Work Unit of Kampar Regency. This research found that simultaneously leadership style, professionalism, work environment, emotional intelligence, and spiritual intelligence have a significant effect on the performance of financial managers at the SKPD Kampar Regency. Meanwhile, partially, Leadership Style has a significant effect on the performance of financial managers. Professionalism has a significant effect on the performance of financial managers. The work environment has a significant effect on the performance of financial managers. Emotional intelligence has no significant effect on the performance of financial managers. Spiritual intelligence has a significant effect on the performance of financial managers. Based on the frequency of responses from research respondents, the dominant answer to the Work Professionalism variable is that respondents agree if employees can plan work, provide feedback, and create jobs. Employees have innovation in completing work, and employees have communication skills. Professionalism must exist in employees; employees must work professionally by providing services without discrimination. They must provide the same service to all employees whose work is related to others, such as investment companies, labor, and industry, all must be treated professionally and fairly without favoring anyone. Besides, employees must be skilled in communicating and planning work.

Individual Characteristics have a significant effect on the Performance of Employees of the Investment and Integrated One-Stop Services Office, Transmigration, and Labor of Balangan Regency, South Kalimantan Province. The findings of this study are in line with research conducted by Popi Rizki Amelia Salsabila (2022) on the Effect of Individual Characteristics, Work Environment, and Job Satisfaction on the Performance of Employees of the Department of Cooperatives, SMEs, and Trade of Tegal City. This research found that: (1) There is a positive and significant influence of individual characteristics on the performance of employees of the Department of Cooperatives, SMEs, and Trade of Tegal City. (2) There is a positive and significant influence of the work environment on the performance of employees of the Department of Cooperatives, SMEs, and Trade of Tegal City. (3) There is a positive and significant influence of job satisfaction on the performance of employees of the Department of Cooperatives, SMEs, and Trade of Tegal City. (4) There is a positive and significant influence of individual characteristics, work environment, and job

satisfaction simultaneously or together on the performance of employees of the Department of Cooperatives, SMEs, and Trade of Tegal City. Based on the frequency of responses from research respondents, the dominant answer to the Individual Characteristics variable is that respondents strongly agree if employees have good abilities in working. Employees rate the job as satisfying and enjoyable, and employees have a good attitude at work. Employees have a high interest in their work. Every employee's individual characteristics must be a good person, such as all employees must have good abilities at work, starting from understanding the work performed by employees to completing the work. All individuals must be good and in accordance with the rules. This can be done starting from oneself to the support of superiors and organizations so that employees can work well. Additionally, liking the job and the organization is something that employees must have because if employees like their work and are satisfied with the results, employees will continue to be encouraged to work well.

Individual Characteristics as the Dominant Influencing Variable on Performance

Based on the research findings, as evidenced by the proof of hypothesis III above, Individual Characteristics significantly influence the performance of employees in the Department of Investment and Integrated One-Stop Services, Transmigration, and Labor of Balangan Regency, South Kalimantan Province. This research discovery is novel, as there is no similarity with previous studies, and it is recommended for consideration in future research. The individual characteristics of employees in the Department of Investment and Integrated One-Stop Services, Transmigration, and Labor of Balangan Regency, South Kalimantan Province, need improvement. This improvement should start with individual awareness to work effectively, develop a liking for their job, and derive satisfaction from their work. Additionally, employees should feel comfortable working within the organization. When employees are comfortable, they are more likely to consistently deliver their best performance in their roles within the organization.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the research and discussion, the following conclusions can be drawn:

1. Simultaneously, Emotional Intelligence, Work Professionalism, and Individual Characteristics have a significant effect on the performance of employees in the Department of Investment and Integrated One-Stop Services, Transmigration, and Labor of Balangan Regency, South Kalimantan Province.
2. Partially, Emotional Intelligence, Work Professionalism, and Individual Characteristics have a significant effect on the performance of employees in the Department of Investment and Integrated One-Stop Services, Transmigration, and Labor of Balangan Regency, South Kalimantan Province.
3. The variable that dominantly influences the performance of employees in the Department of Investment and Integrated One-Stop Services, Transmigration, and Labor of Balangan Regency, South Kalimantan Province, is Individual Characteristics.

RECOMMENDATION

Based on the results of the discussion and conclusions, the recommendations from the results of this research are:

1. Emotional Intelligence is a variable that significantly influences the performance of employees in the Department of Investment and Integrated One-Stop Services, Transmigration, and Labor of Balangan Regency, South Kalimantan Province. In the future, Emotional Intelligence should be possessed by all employees. Guidance and evaluation of work should be continuously carried out by the organization so that employees can work by controlling their emotions and continue to innovate and empathize in their work.
2. In addition to Emotional Intelligence, Work Professionalism is a variable that significantly influences the performance of employees in the Department of Investment and Integrated One-Stop Services, Transmigration, and Labor of Balangan Regency, South Kalimantan Province. In the future, employees should be professional in their work, taking full responsibility for what is their duty and not passing it on to other employees.
3. In addition to Emotional Intelligence and Professionalism, Individual Characteristics are also variables that significantly and dominantly influence the performance of employees in the Department of Investment and Integrated One-Stop Services, Transmigration, and Labor of Balangan Regency, South Kalimantan Province. In the future, individual employees should have a positive attitude, be kind, and have a high interest in what they do.
4. The performance of employees in the Department of Investment and Integrated One-Stop Services, Transmigration, and Labor

of Balangan Regency, South Kalimantan Province is influenced by Emotional Intelligence, Work Professionalism, and Individual Characteristics by 26.5%, while the remaining 73.5% is influenced by other factors. For future research, it is recommended to add other variables that affect employee performance besides Emotional Intelligence, Work Professionalism, and Individual Characteristics.

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